

Understanding and satisfying the requirements for facilitating iStar modeling: a tool-supported modeling process

Supplemental material

I. MODELING RESULTS FROM BEGINNERS

The average time spent on the tutorial sessions was 24 minutes. We used the same material to introduce each beginner to the iStar modeling framework. One of the authors gave the tutorial to each beginner to ensure consistency. After the tutorial, beginners could ask any questions they had, and we answered them until they felt they completely understood. The difference in time spent on the tutorial session comes from the Q&A activity.

B8 built the smallest model, and B10 took the shortest modeling time. The online judge platform developed by B2 and B3 was the most complex software system in this case study. Thus the iStar model constructed by these two participants had the most model elements. Specifically, although B2 and B3 developed the software system together, they participated in our case study separately. B2 took 30 minutes longer to model than B3, with a finer granularity of the actors' intentions in their scenario leading to more intentional elements and refinements. That is why the final model that B2 built contains more elements than B3.

Refinements between intentional elements were most commonly used in the models finalized by beginners. The number of intentional elements reflecting the goals, tasks, and required resources of actors, and the number of refinements, were the highest model elements in each beginner's model. In the models from beginners, there were about three actors. The dependencies between actors ranged from zero to twelve, with an average of four dependencies. It is worth noting that all the beginners did not use is-a or participates-in relationships between actors during modeling. One possible reason is that they can complete the requirements modeling around several specific roles (e.g., teacher, student). There is no need to use the participants-in relationship to associate these roles with a specific individual.

II. ANSWERING RQ2

RQ2: What are the modeling processes you use?

The modeling process used by beginners is as follows. We use the letter D for numbering, where D stands for difficulties.

- B1 Begin by listing all the user requirements that can be thought of at once and then elicit the system requirements. The user requirements are presented as the user actor

and its intentional elements. The system requirements are presented as the system actor and its intentional elements. Use dependencies to represent the process of eliciting system requirements.

- B2 Generally, the modeling process goes from abstract and loose analysis to concrete and logical decomposition. First, consider the actors in the scenario and the coarsest-grained dependencies between them. Then consider the requirements of each actor. Analyze the actors presenting most requirements first, and elicit the entities implementing these requirements.
- B3 Consider the actors' intentions individually and then consider their dependencies.
- B4 Consider the actors' intentions individually and then consider their dependencies.
- B5 The overall process is abstract and then concrete. If B5 has a global understanding of all requirements, B5 will start modeling from the whole first. If B5 is only familiar with local requirements, B5 will start modeling from the local. Modeling from the whole to the local is to analyze each requirement and build all the associated elements. Modeling from local to the whole is to analyze the requirements of each actor in the scenario. Then analyze the connections between these requirements.
- B6 First, clarify the subject, then clarify which elements the actors will involve, and then decompose tasks and goals, and finally consider the relationship between elements. Preferences are top-down, step-by-step decomposition.
- B7 First of all, determine all the actors, and then start to decompose from the top-level goal of each actor, and gradually refine it until it is refined into atomic goals or tasks, then allocate resources, and finally identify the dependencies between goals, subjects or tasks to yield the complete iStar model. In the modeling process, usually determine the general framework first, such as determining the actor and top-level goals, and then refine other intentions.
- B8 First, model the goals, for they are easier to determine. Second, determine the tasks based on those goals, decomposing the entire requirements into smaller ones. Finally, determine the relationship between actors and intentions.
- B9 The modeling process is first to determine which actors

are involved, then determine the main goal of each actor and then consider how to subdivide the sub-tasks and the relationship between them for each goal.

- B10 First, clarify the actor, then find out the key functions (the highest-level requirements), and then gradually refine the goal from top to bottom.

III. ANSWERING RQ3

RQ3: What are the difficulties of iStar modeling in practice?

The main difficulties encountered by beginners are as follows.

- B1 D1 Analyzing the requirements, abstracting, and extracting model elements from them is the most difficult.
D2 The way to express timing relationships with iStar
D3 Some practical needs are difficult to express with iStar.
D4 It is difficult to determine the starting point for modeling analysis.
D5 The way to break some intentional elements down
- B2 D1 Abstraction and determination of requirements from actual scenarios and determination of correspondence between models and reality
D2 Determine the level of abstraction between requirements (intentional elements).
D3 Finding out the root requirements and finding all the requirements as leaf nodes
D4 Layout affects modeling ideas, and hand-drawn models on paper are troublesome.
D5 User requirements are not completely determined.
- B3 D1 Abstraction and classification of intentional elements in actors
D2 Splitting and merging of intentional elements
D3 Expression of timing relationships, actor internal dependencies, creation, and origin of resources
D4 Clear and accurate description of requirements
- B4 D1 Learning model semantics, graphical representation, and syntax
D2 Hand-drawn models
D3 Distinction between goals and tasks
D4 Distinction of conceptual levels of intention elements
D5 Naming for the more abstract intention elements formed
D6 Naming for Dependendum
D7 The requirements analysis ability and the requirements document quality affect the modeling difficulty.
- B5 D1 High learning cost and complex graphical notations, but semantics and notations are not difficult to understand
D2 Compared with the abstraction of class diagrams and flowcharts, iStar abstraction is more involved. Both the code's functionality and a software system's external performance have to be considered.
D3 The level and the quality of understanding of requirements affect the modeling difficulty.
- B6 D1 Distinction relationships to use among actors.
D2 Clarify the definition of relationships.
- B7 D1 Clarify all the concepts of iStar models.

D2 Clarify the concepts of dependency relationship.

B8 None.

- B9 D1 iStar requires a certain amount of abstract thinking.
D2 Distinguish different kinds of relations.
D3 Distinguish different kinds of actors.
D4 Clarify the directions of relationships.
- B10 D1 Clarify all the concepts of iStar models.
D2 Help users to clarify and refine the requirements.
D3 Distinguish different kinds of actors.
D4 Distinguish different kinds of relationships.

IV. ANSWERING RQ5

RQ5: What requirements do you have for an iStar modeling tool?

The requirements of beginners for the iStar modeling tool are as follows.

- B1 R1 Intelligent Modeling: Automatic Extraction of Model Elements
R2 Forces modelers to think using heuristic questions
R3 Bidirectional Data binding from requirements list to iStar models
R4 List all dependencies between two actors and generate models in batches
R5 Check some of the intentional elements and highlight the elements associated with them
- B2 R1 Require the user to list all imaginable requirements in the form of intentional elements in a template or list without considering the hierarchical relationship between requirements
R2 Need to be guided by the modeling process at the top level, especially the first step to start modeling. For example, it could be to ask the user to think about what actors are in the scenario and to specify at least one actor in the scenario
R3 Can flexibly adjust the position of elements in the model
R4 Automatic layout
R5 Automatically generate graphical model elements for the requirements list mentioned in Point 1
- B3 R1 Automatically organize the connection of relationships in the model to avoid messy connections
- B4 R1 Present information about the semantic, graphical representation of each model element in the modeling tool
R2 Check the model syntax in the tool
R3 Automatic layout
R4 Display the requirements of each actor in a list, uniformly generate intentional elements, the specific type of the elements can be ignored at the adding time
R5 Give operational ways to distinguish between goals and tasks or give explicit modeling guidance
R6 Provide naming templates for intentional elements and Dependendum
- B5 R1 Model componentization, support for reuse, e.g., for the decomposition of the Query function, provide templates in the standard component library

- R2 Provide demos and examples of models and support multiple languages (especially Chinese documentation)
- R3 Maintain an active community
- R4 Support modeling from requirements documents to iStar models
- R5 Provide automatic layout for large models, presenting the general direction of the modeling
- R6 Provide personalized views for different users of the same model. For example, developers and product managers focus on different content
- B6 R1 Define a condensed model without complex elements and relationships for beginners.
 - R2 Provide hints of decent element type applicable when modeling.
 - R3 Provide extra instructions and examples to help beginners understand iStar better.
- B7 R1 Support adjusts the layout of the models to implement visualization.
 - R2 Support syntax checking based on the restrictions of different notations.
 - R3 Highlight important functionalities and messages.
 - R4 Support auto layout functionality to make the view of the model clearer.
- B8 R1 Hint the definition and modeling method of the selected relationship.
 - R2 Support auto layout functionality to save time.
- B9 R1 Provide a small tooltip to switch the direction of relationships.
 - R2 Support auto layout functionality to adjust the position in batch.
 - R3 Support functionality to identify elements from uploaded documents.
- B10 R1 Check syntax and automatically correct errors.
 - R2 Generate models automatically based on uploaded requirement text.
 - R3 Support auto layout functionality.

V. MODELING

Following are the three new ways of adding model elements.

- Add elements in batches (satisfies requirements R2)

We have designed batch-add methods for dependencies, refinements, and intentional elements in actors. The two relationships, dependency and refinement, are the two most important and commonly used relationships in iStar modeling, while the intentional elements reflect the requirements of actors. In the future, other batch addition methods for other model elements can be added according to practical needs. In our proposed modeling process, if a modeler wants to add multiple dependencies between two actors, the modeler only needs to select these two actors and then list the dependencies between them (in the form of text) so that the addition of model elements will be completed. According to our proposed modeling process, the visualization of the batch-added model elements can be done automatically in the next part, the visualization and interaction part. Modelers can similarly add refinements. Moreover, we allow modelers to select any actor

to add intentional elements, i.e., batch addition of intentional elements. In this activity, modelers only need to consider actors' intentions and not need to consider what relationships exist between these intentions. We believe modelers can enumerate any actor's intention, i.e., its requirements, simply and quickly in this way.

- Add model templates to add elements (satisfies requirements R3)

The key to adding model elements with model templates is to design practical templates. Based on the empirical experience we gained, providing generic, domain-specific, and model elements named templates will meet the requirements R3.1, R3.2, and R3.3. Meanwhile, these templates will cover the actual iStar modeling scenarios better. The construction of the template library will take time and require the long-term efforts of many iStar modeling experts and domain experts. The final completed template library will be a domain knowledge base. In this paper, we take the first step toward that goal. We have designed a modeling template for a generic scenario to guide modelers through an in-depth analysis of its requirements. Specifically, the generic scenario is that a Product Manager (PM) is looking for programmers to develop Software for Users. We posed three heuristic questions for its requirements analysis and iStar modeling process.

- 1) What TASKs do Users depend on Software to do?
- 2) What RESOURCES does Software depend on Users to get?
- 3) What GOREs does the Owner (i.e., the PM in this scenario) depend on Software to achieve?

These three heuristic questions can effectively lead modelers to take the first step in analyzing the requirements in this scenario. The modeling template in this generic scenario includes three actors (Users, Software, and Owners) and the dependencies between these three actors. Such a template satisfies requirements R3.1 and R1.3.

- Add elements from SRSs (satisfies requirements R4)

Some practical software projects have mature and complete software requirements specifications (SRSs). It is not economical to create iStar models for these projects entirely manually. The manual modeling process inevitably introduces errors and oversights. We should allow our modelers to focus as much as possible on the key elements, but not every element of the model. Therefore, we specifically designed the process of adding model elements from SRS for such modeling scenarios. We hope that state-of-art natural language processing and machine learning technologies can help modelers complete the document-to-model conversion process. Specifically, one modeler inputs the SRS, and there are methods and tools to automatically extract model elements from it and complete the addition of model elements.

VI. QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ISTAR BEGINNERS

- 1) Please write down your name.
- 2) Describe the functionality of the software project for which you are the lead developer in one sentence.

- 3) You developed this project over a period of time of:
 - A. Less than a month
 - B. More than a month, but less than a quarter
 - C. More than a quarter, but less than half a year
 - D. More than half a year, but less than a year
 - E. More than a year
- 4) In addition to automatically generated code (such as boilerplate code), the estimated number of lines of code you write while developing this project are:
 - A. Less than 1000
 - B. 1000~5000
 - C. 5000~10000
 - D. More than 10000
- 5) Please describe the programming language and tech stack used to develop the project.
- 6) Do you do continuous iterations during the development process?
 - A. No, I just finished the software in one go
 - B. Partially, I finish the core functionality of the software in one go and have a few bug fixes after that
 - C. Yes, I finished the development of the software in some iterations and fixed some bugs after the completion without developing new functionalities
 - D. Yes, I keep iterating to develop the software, including new functionalities and bug fixes
- 7) How long has this project you developed been up and running?
 - A. Less than half a year
 - B. More than half a year but less than a year
 - C. More than a year but less than two years
 - D. More than two years
- 8) How many users have already used this software you developed?
 - A. Less than 100
 - B. 100~200
 - C. 200~300
 - D. 300~400
 - E. More than 400
- 9) To what extent is your software project meeting the requirements of the users?
 - A. Not at all satisfied
 - B. Slightly satisfied
 - C. Moderately satisfied
 - D. Very satisfied
 - E. Completely satisfied